

Topological Analysis of the “El Niño” Phenomenon

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Abstract—This study uses Topological Data Analysis (TDA) for a detailed examination of the El Niño phenomenon. Time-delay embedding algorithms, the Mapper technique, and Markov chains were applied to anomaly data from the Niño 3.4 region, revealing persistent patterns and cycles. Distinct clusters representing El Niño events, La Niña events, and normal conditions were clearly identified. In addition, an atypical cluster of particularly warm El Niño events was discovered, among which the devastating 1997 phenomenon stands out.

Index Terms—El Niño Phenomenon, Topological Data Analysis (TDA), Mapper Algorithm, Markov Chains, Climate Modeling

I. CONTEXT AND MOTIVATION

El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) is a periodic fluctuation of ocean surface temperature and atmospheric air pressure in the equatorial region of the Pacific Ocean. When the phenomenon occurs, the pressure change causes an east-to-west air circulation. This generates high sea-surface temperatures in the west and heavy precipitation in Australia and along the west coast [1].

ENSO has significant global repercussions, affecting climate patterns, agriculture, marine ecosystems, and even the economy. During El Niño episodes, regions that normally experience dry climates may receive intense rainfall and vice versa. This phenomenon can therefore lead to severe droughts or floods, affecting food production and causing a variety of socioeconomic problems [2].

In this study, we explore how Topological Data Analysis (TDA), a relatively new branch of data science, can be useful for analyzing ENSO. TDA allows us to examine the “shape” of data, providing a unique view of its structure and underlying relationships.

II. DATA CLEANING AND FEATURE SELECTION

The dataset used in this study was obtained from the National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI). This dataset underwent a series of cleaning and preprocessing steps to prepare it for analysis. The selected variables from this dataset include:

- **Southern Oscillation Index (SOI):** A standard measure of the magnitude and intensity of the Southern Oscillation. Negative values indicate the warm phase (El Niño), and positive values indicate the cold phase (La Niña) of the Southern Oscillation.
- **Oceanic Niño Index (ONI):** The Southern Oscillation measure used to officially identify El Niño (positive values) and La Niña (negative values) events.
- **Sea Surface Temperature (SST):** Represents sea-surface temperature, a key indicator of El Niño and Southern Oscillation conditions.

- **Outgoing Longwave Radiation (OLR):** A measure of the amount of energy being radiated into space from Earth and its atmosphere.

The original variables from Niño regions 1 and 2 were removed due to their lack of relevance for this study. Additionally, it was decided to use only the columns representing SOI and OLR anomalies, since they showed very high correlation with their respective standardized and original versions; this selection helps avoid multicollinearity in the model.

An important part of the data cleaning was the transformation of the year and month columns. In some cases, the year column was adjusted based on the season, and the months were mapped to their corresponding numeric values to facilitate analysis.

For the analysis, the focus was placed on the **Niño 3.4 index**. This index is considered by many climatologists to be the most representative of ENSO, since the Niño 3.4 region is located in the equatorial Pacific, where the most significant temperature changes occur during El Niño and La Niña events.

Once the data are loaded, a statistical description of ENSO index values is produced, providing information about the mean, standard deviation, minimum value, maximum value, among others. This helps develop an idea of the data distribution and can be useful to identify irregularities or anomalies.

Additionally, to facilitate analysis, the time series is smoothed using a moving average. This is done to reduce noise and short-term fluctuations in the data, and to highlight long-term trends. The moving average is calculated as follows:

$$M_t = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_{t-n} \quad (1)$$

where M_t is the moving average at time t , N is the window size (in this case, 6 months), and x_{t-n} are the time-series values at previous time points.

Finally, these smoothed ENSO index values are used for **Takens embeddings**, a procedure used to reconstruct a phase space from a one-dimensional time series. This technique is particularly useful for analyzing dynamical systems and is essential for ENSO analysis.

III. PERSISTENT HOMOLOGY

According to NOAA, ENSO is a periodic fluctuation that occurs every two to seven years in sea-surface temperature. However, the detailed recurrence of this phenomenon is not fully known.

Given this, a persistent homology analysis is conducted with the purpose of analyzing ENSO periodicity topologically

and in greater detail. For this, anomaly data from the Niño 3.4 region are used. Likewise, the time-delay parameter is defined as $\tau = 16$ and the dimension as $d = 8$, since these were found to be the optimal parameters for this analysis. For dimensionality reduction, a **False Nearest Neighbors** analysis was performed, from which it was determined that it is possible to use dimension 3 for persistence analysis. This was performed for all analyzed time series, and the result was the same: using dimension 3 was feasible.

Before showing the persistent homology analysis, Fig. 1 presents the time series used.

Fig. 1. Time Series of the ENSO Index

Taking this into account, Fig. 2 presents the embedding of the ENSO index time series, and Fig. 3 the persistence diagram.

Fig. 2. Time-Series Embedding with $\tau = 16$ and $d = 3$

Fig. 3. Persistence Diagram

As can be seen in Fig. 3, there are several H_1 points that persist over time, indicating the existence of two-dimensional holes and therefore periodicity in the data. However, this is not easily appreciated in Fig. 2, so the time series is smoothed using a moving average with a window of 6. Doing this produces what is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Smoothed Time Series

Using this time series, Fig. 5 presents the resulting embedding.

Fig. 5. Embedding of the Smoothed Time Series with $\tau = 17$ and $d = 3$

Fig. 7. Persistence Diagram of the Smoothed Time Series (First 120 months)

From this figure, the holes around the embedding can be better appreciated. However, this becomes clearer if the series is divided into different periods.

Therefore, the smoothed time series was divided into periods of 120 months (10 years). Figs. 6 and 7 present the embeddings and persistence diagrams, respectively, for the first 120 months.

Figs. 8 and 9 present the embeddings for the next 120 months and the last 120 months, respectively.

Fig. 6. Embedding of the Smoothed Time Series (First 120 months) with $\tau = 4$ and $d = 3$

Fig. 8. Embedding of the Smoothed Time Series (Second 120 months) with $\tau = 6$ and $d = 3$

Fig. 9. Embedding of the Smoothed Time Series (Last 120 months) with $\tau = 3$ and $d = 3$

As can be observed, there are clearly holes in all previously presented embeddings, which indicates that in each time period there are cycles. An important observation is the existence of cycles of different sizes; this may indicate the presence of multiple cycles with different time periods.

IV. MAPPER ALGORITHM

We used the Mapper algorithm to visualize the connections that exist between different groups of months, and to determine whether they belong to an El Niño period, a La Niña period, or a regular period. To build Mapper, we used sea-level temperatures and their anomalies from regions 3, 3.4, and 4; we also used SOI, OLR, and ONI information. For projection, ONI index anomalies were used because this index indicates whether the system is currently in El Niño, La Niña, or neither. A cover of 4 hypercubes with 20% overlap was used. Finally, K-means was used as the clustering technique, and 3 clusters were defined, since there are three possible states: El Niño, La Niña, or neither.

Fig. 10 shows the resulting Mapper graph.

Fig. 10. Mapper

In the visualization above, we can see several nodes with certain connections. Yellow nodes represent El Niño, purple nodes represent La Niña, and blue nodes represent a normal period. The months were grouped according to the OLR index. Within these data, we can observe an anomaly: although in general El Niño is on the left side of the graph, there is one case where it appears on the opposite side. This node corresponds to the El Niño phenomenon that occurred between 1997 and 1998, which was unusually strong, with devastating consequences, including the death of 16% of coral worldwide.

V. MARKOV CHAIN

Thanks to the graph shown by Mapper, we can visually observe behavior over the years. It was found that in order to go from El Niño to La Niña (or vice versa), it is necessary to pass through a normal state. To provide a better analysis and understanding of this, a Markov chain was generated to provide a numerical representation. The goal is to visualize transition probabilities between temperature ranges of ONI anomaly values. Different intervals were defined as states; these represent recorded temperatures. This was done to better visualize behavior and the probabilities that temperature transitions between El Niño, a normal state, or La Niña.

The following temperature intervals were defined:

- 1) $< -2^\circ$
- 2) -2° to -1.5°
- 3) -1.5° to -1°
- 4) -1° to -0.5°
- 5) -0.5° to 0°
- 6) 0° to 0.5°
- 7) 0.5° to 1°
- 8) 1° to 1.5°
- 9) 1.5° to 2°
- 10) $> 2^\circ$

- **Blue:** La Niña.
- **Gray:** Normal.
- **Red:** El Niño.

As a result, we obtained the following graph:

Fig. 11. Markov Chain

The stationary probabilities were also obtained as follows:

- 1) 0.0009
- 2) 0.0213
- 3) 0.0667
- 4) 0.1796
- 5) 0.2407
- 6) 0.2268
- 7) 0.1524
- 8) 0.0582
- 9) 0.0349

10) 0.0186

We can observe that to move from one extreme to the other—i.e., from El Niño to La Niña or vice versa—it is necessary to pass through a normal state. It was also found that the lowest stationary probabilities correspond to the extremes, while probabilities increase toward the midpoint.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

After studying ENSO, we conclude the following:

- There is indeed periodicity in ENSO, which can be clearly observed in the persistence diagrams of the three 120-month intervals shown in Section III.
- The **Outgoing Longwave Radiation (OLR)** variable is very important when applying the Mapper algorithm in Section IV. Fig. 10 indicates the graph obtained by Mapper, which reveals a node representing a group of El Niño records with **positive OLR** between 1997 and 1998. This is considered an anomaly because El Niño records are associated with **negative OLR** [1]. After investigating these records, we identified that this El Niño event was one of the most destructive, deeply affecting life and public health in Latin American countries [3].
- The Markov chain reinforces the idea found via Mapper: it is not possible to transition from El Niño to La Niña without first passing through a “normal” weather state. However, the Markov chain reveals that once a state with temperature greater than 2° is reached, it is highly likely to remain in that same state, although the probability of reaching it is relatively low. On the other hand, stationary probabilities indicate that in the long run it is likely to remain in states 5 or 6, which refer to “normal” conditions in which neither El Niño nor La Niña occurs.

VII. FUTURE WORK

This study has revealed the potential of Topological Data Analysis to examine and uncover patterns in the El Niño phenomenon. However, we believe that integrating more sophisticated time-series modeling techniques can significantly increase the predictive capacity and understanding of this climate phenomenon.

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Neural Networks:

These models present a promising horizon for future work. They are especially good at handling sequential data such as the time series used in our analysis [4]. In particular, LSTM models can learn from past temporal patterns in the data, which could significantly improve the ability to predict the occurrence and duration of El Niño [5]. Implementing this deep learning approach could allow for more accurate long-term predictions, providing sufficient time for preparations to mitigate the impacts of El Niño events.

Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)

Models: These could also be implemented in future studies. ARIMA models, and particularly their seasonal variant (SARIMA), are widely recognized tools for time-series analysis and forecasting [6]. They could be used to analyze ocean temperature anomaly time series and predict the occurrence

of El Niño. ARIMA models can efficiently capture and model autocorrelation in the time-series data, which can further improve forecasting accuracy.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Oceanic and A. A. (NOAA), “El Niño/Southern Oscillation (ENSO),” 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/monitoring/enso/>
- [2] IPCC, “Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part B: Regional Aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change,” 2014, accessed: 2023-06-05. Available: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar5/wg2/>
- [3] P. A. H. Organization, “Fenómeno El Niño, 1997–1998,” 2000.
- [4] S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, “Long short-term memory,” pp. 1735–1780, 1997.
- [5] Z. Che, S. Purushotham, K. Cho, D. Sontag, and Y. Liu, “Recurrent neural networks for multivariate time series with missing values,” 2018.
- [6] G. E. Box, G. M. Jenkins, G. C. Reinsel, and G. M. Ljung, “Time series analysis: Forecasting and control,” 2015.